

PEDAGOGIK VA PSIXOLOGIK TADQIQOTLAR

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ И ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14609563>

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES (ESP) FOR ADULTS

ANNOTATION

In this article we look through the teaching methods of ESP to adults which is a dynamic and specialized field that requires a tailored approach, considering the professional needs and experiences of learners. In contrast general English, ESP is goal-oriented, catering to adult learners who need English skills for a specific context-whether it's business, law, medicine, engineering, or other areas.

Key words: teaching methods of ESP, dynamic and specialized field, tailored approach, goal-oriented, specific context, catering to adult learners.

МЕТОДИКА ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА ДЛЯ СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫХ ЦЕЛЕЙ ДЛЯ ВЗРОСЛЫХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье мы рассмотрим методы преподавания ESP для взрослых, которое представляет собой динамичную и специализированную область, требующую индивидуального подхода с учетом профессиональных потребностей и опыта учащихся. В отличие от общего английского, ESP целенаправленно ориентирован на взрослых учащихся, которым необходимы навыки английского языка для конкретного контекста - будь то бизнес, право, медицина, инженерное дело или другие области.

Ключевые слова: методика преподавания ESP, динамическая и специализированная область, индивидуальный подход, целенаправленно ориентирован, конкретный контекст, на взрослых учащихся.

INGLIZ TILINI ANIQ O'QITISH METODIKASI KATTALAR UCHUN MAQSADLAR (ESP)

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada biz talabalarning kasbiy ehtiyojlari va tajribasiga asoslangan individual yondashuvni talab qiluvchi dinamik va ixtisoslashgan soha bo'lgan ESPni kattalarga o'rgatish usullarini ko'rib chiqamiz. Umumiy ingliz tilidan farqli o'laroq, ESP maxsus kontekstda - biznes, huquq, tibbiyot, muhandislik yoki boshqa sohalarida ingliz tilini bilishga muhtoj bo'lgan kattalar o'quvchilariga mo'ljallangan.

Kalit so'zlar: ESP o'qitish metodikasi, dinamik va ixtisoslashtirilgan soha, individual yondashuv, maqsadga yo'naltirilgan, aniq kontekst, katta yoshli o'quvchilarga.

Introduction

English for Specific Purposes (ESP) is a branch of English language teaching that focuses on developing learners' proficiency in English tailored to specific professional or academic fields. Unlike general English, ESP is goal-oriented, catering to adult learners who need English skills for a specific context-whether it's business, law, medicine, engineering, or other areas. Teaching ESP to adults requires specialized approaches, combining language instruction with the demands of the learner's target field. There are some key principles of ESP methodology which we can go through them below.

First and the main one is needs analysis which is the cornerstone of ESP teaching. It involves determining the specific needs of learners, their existing language proficiency, and the target skills they need to develop.

In an adult ESP class, needs vary widely based on the learners' professional backgrounds. For instance, a group of business professionals may need to focus on writing emails, negotiating, or giving presentations in English, whereas healthcare workers may prioritize medical terminology and patient interaction. Conducting interviews, surveys, or language assessments can help teachers design a curriculum that addresses these unique needs.

Second and the main point of ESP methodology is contextualized learning which involves integrating language learning with the content and context of the learner's field. The teacher must design lessons and materials that reflect real-world language usage in that specific profession. For example, in an ESP class for engineers, lessons might focus on technical vocabulary, writing reports, or reading technical manuals.

By using authentic materials such as industry reports, business letters, or medical case studies, teachers can help learners see the immediate relevance of English to their work, which motivates adult learners.

Third and more important one is task-based learning (TBL) which is a highly effective approach in ESP methodology, as it encourages learners to use English in real-life situations similar to those they will face in their jobs.

This methodology allows learners to practice language through problem-solving tasks directly related to their field. For example, in a legal English course, learners could role-play contract negotiations or work on drafting legal documents. Task-based learning helps adult learners become more proficient in their specific areas of work by simulating professional tasks and using field-specific language.

Other of the main principles of ESP methodology is learner autonomy. Adult learners typically bring a wealth of professional experience to the classroom, and they often prefer having some degree of control over their learning process.

ESP teaching should therefore encourage learner autonomy by providing opportunities for self-directed learning.

This can include assigning research tasks where learners explore materials related to their profession or encouraging them to use online resources or professional networks to practice English. By fostering autonomy, the teacher empowers adults to take charge of their own learning, aligning with their professional development goals.

Another of the key points of these methodology is skill integration which ESP courses focus on integrating the four core language skills-reading, writing, speaking, and listening-in a way that reflects the demands of the specific professional or academic setting.

Unlike general English classes, which may focus on each skill separately, ESP often involves using multiple skills simultaneously. For example, a business English learner might need to read financial reports (reading), discuss them in meetings (speaking), take notes (writing), and follow up on complex discussions (listening). Skill integration is crucial to preparing learners to function effectively in their professional contexts.

One of the leading principles is collaborative learning that adults in ESP courses often have extensive knowledge of their specific fields, which can enrich the learning process. Teachers can encourage collaboration among learners by organizing group projects or discussions where participants share insights from their professional experiences. This collaborative approach not only builds language skills but also creates a sense of community in the classroom. For example, healthcare professionals can discuss case studies or share best practices in their fields, using English to communicate their ideas.

One and the other major point of ESP teaching methods is assessment and feedback which refers to assess the learner's specific objectives in ESP. Traditional language proficiency tests may not adequately reflect the progress of an ESP learner.

Instead, teachers should design assessments based on the learner's professional tasks, such as giving presentations, writing reports, or participating in meetings. Feedback should be ongoing and tailored to help learners improve in areas that are directly relevant to their jobs. For instance, providing feedback on an engineer's technical report might focus on clarity, terminology accuracy, and coherence rather than general grammar mistakes.

Results

Research experience have some results on facing with number of difficulties in using above mentioned methods for teaching ESP to adults, such as diverse backgrounds, specialized knowledge, balancing language and content.

1. Adult learners in ESP classes often have varying degrees of expertise in their fields and English proficiency levels. It can be challenging to create lessons that cater to all levels. Differentiated instruction and personalized learning plans can help mitigate this issue.

2. Teachers may not always be experts in the specific fields their learners are engaged in, which can make preparing relevant materials challenging. Teachers should collaborate with field experts or consult specialized resources to ensure their materials are accurate and appropriate.

3. It's important to strike a balance between teaching the specific content of the learner's profession and focusing on language development. If too much emphasis is placed on content, language learning may suffer, and if too much focus is on language, the specific needs of the profession may not be addressed.

Conclusion

Teaching ESP to adults is a dynamic and specialized field that requires a tailored approach, considering the professional needs and experiences of learners. By focusing on needs analysis, contextualized learning, task-based activities, and learner autonomy, teachers can create highly relevant and engaging learning experiences.

Despite its challenges, ESP offers adults the opportunity to enhance their professional capabilities through targeted English language development, opening doors for career advancement and personal growth.

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